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Review of ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) of the Dodecanese Archipelago, Greece

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5571270>

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Abstract: Based on published records and new materials, we confirm presence of 110 ant species from the Dodecanese. The fauna of ants of the Dodecanese is distinct in relation to the other Greek provinces. Six species are insular endemics, and 19 species or morphospecies are known only from this archipelago. Four species are recorded from the Dodecanese for the first time. Additionally, *Bothriomyrmex jannonei* MENOZZI, 1936 is synonymized with *Bothriomyrmex communista* SANTSCHI, 1919, **new synonymy**.

Key words: ants, Greece, Dodecanese, taxonomy, faunistics.

INTRODUCTION

This paper is the next one focused on the faunistic review of Greek regions. Previous papers noted ants of the Greek islands: Cephalonia (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2014a), Corfu (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2021a), Crete (SALATA *et al.* 2020), Euboea (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018e), Samos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018c), Zakynthos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018d), and continental provinces: Epirus (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018a), Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017a), Thrace (BRAČKO *et al.* 2016), Thessaly (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018b) and the Western Greece (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2021b). Numerous new faunistic records were also given in several faunistic and taxonomic papers focused on Greek ants (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012, 2013, 2014b, 2017b, CsÖSZ *et al.* 2018, SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017, 2018a, 2018b, 2019a, 2019b, 2019c, SALATA *et al.* 2018a, b, SALATA *et al.* 2019). This paper is based mainly on the new material collected by Lech Borowiec and Sebastian Salata on Karpathos, Rhodes, and Kos, materials preserved in Natural History Museum of Crete, Iraklion (Greece), Upper Silesian Museum, Bytom (Poland), private collection of Petr Werner, Prague (Czech Republic) and materials collected by Claude Lebas, Canohès (France) donated to the collection of the Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław (Poland). Verified published data from the Dodecanese have also been included.

STUDY AREA

The Dodecanese Islands are a group of 15 large and 150 small Greek islands located at the southeastern part of the Aegean Sea and spread along the coast of Turkey's Anatolia. The four largest islands are: Rhodes (1401.46 km²), Karpathos (300.152 km²), Kos (287.611 km²), and Kalymnos (110.581 km²), the rest have an area below 100 km². As many as 26 islands are inhabited. The four largest islands have a various number of inhabitants, from 6,200 in Karpathos to 115,000 in Rhodes. On smaller islands, the number of inhabitants does not exceed 3,050. The total population of the Dodecanese is 16,2493, with Rhodes island as its capital. The geography of the Dodecanese is very diverse on every island. The terrain of the Dodecanese islands is infertile and rocky, and 42% of its total area is flat, 26% is gently sloping, and 32% is mountainous. The highest mountain peaks are Kivaras (1290 m) in Karpathos and Attavyros (1240 m) in Rhodes. Dominant rocks are limestones and black schist limestones surrounded by shales and sandstones. Rocks made of alternating lava flow and volcanic materials prevail on some volcanic islands. There are no rivers in the Dodecanese, although one will find running waters and streams in many areas. The Dodecanese is recognized for its volcanic activity with abundant mineral resources. The climate is quite mild, with mild winters and cool summers. Most of the small Dodecanese islands are deforested, thus the vegetation formed on these islands is usually the brushwood and maquis. Generally, the Dodecanese flora consists of species that can endure the arid conditions of the Mediterranean summer and the water shortage. Typical species of brushwood vegetation are the rock roses *Cistus* spp., the aestivate species, and various species of aromatic plants such as the sage *Salvia* spp. and the thyme *Thymus* spp. Typical species of maquis vegetation on the Dodecanese islands are the yew tree *Quercus coccifera*, the pistacia *Pistacia lentiscus*, the carob tree *Ceratonia siliqua*, and *Olea sylvestris*. The forests on large islands are fragmentary, composed of Brutia Pine *Pinus brutia*, the cypress *Cupressus* spp. and the small oaks *Quercus* spp. One of the most typical trees is the Olive tree *Olea europaea*, which is either in a wild state or as a cultivated tree (TRICHAS 2004).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The main method, applied at all sites, was direct sampling (hand collecting). Nests and individual specimens were collected on the ground, in leaf litter, under stones, in dead wood, on tree trunks and twigs. Ants were brushed off to the sweep net on the roadsides and forest. Nests were searched in rocks cracks and searched on cracked rocks using a chisel. All specimens were preserved in pure 75% and 96% ethanol. Published records were also cited but only for taxa whose taxonomic status was verifiable.

Images of ant specimens were taken using a Nikon SMZ 1500 stereomicroscope, Nikon D5200 photo camera, and Helicon Focus software. Distribution in Greece refers to BOROWIEC (2014), SALATA and BOROWIEC (2018), and unpublished data from the Database and Collection of Greek Ants (DCGA), preserved at the University of Wrocław. Distribution outside Greece is noted only for recently described species. Geographical coordinates are given in a decimal system. Materials are deposited in the following institutions:

DSAB—Dipartimento di Scienze Agrarie, Università di Bologna, Bologna, Italy,

MNHW-DBET—Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław, in temporary deposit by Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy, University of Wrocław, Poland – former coll. L. Borowiec,

NHMC—Natural History Museum of Crete, Iraklion, Greece,

USMB—Upper Silesian Museum, Bytom, Poland,

PWC—private collection of Petr Werner, Prague, Czech Republic.

LIST OF LOCALITIES

- DOD_001: Agia Kyriaki, 22 m, 10.06.2005, 36.5475N/ 26.4035E, leg. M. Chatzaki (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_002: Agia Kyriaki, 7 m, 11.06.2005, 36.5475N/ 26.4035E, leg. M. Chatzaki (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_003: Agia Kyriaki n. Astypalaia, 7m, 11.06.2005, 36.5473N/ 26.4027E, leg. M. Chatzaki (MNHW-DBET, NHMC).
- DOD_004: Agia Kyriaki n. Kalymnos, 22m, 10.06.2005, 36.9757N/ 26.9121E, leg. M. Chatzaki (NHMC).
- DOD_005: Armathia, 68 m, 14.02.1992, 35.4374N/ 26.8658E, leg. M. Mylonas (NHMC, MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_006: Gyali, 32 m, 05.06.2005, 36.669N/ 27.1265E, leg. M. Chatzaki (NHMC, MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_007: Kalimnos, Agia Aikaterini, 161 m, 09.06.2005, 36.9366N/ 26.9514E, leg. M. Chatzaki (NHMC).
- DOD_008: Kalimnos, NW of Vathy, 70 m, 09.06.2005, 36.9843N/ 26.9896E, leg. M. Chatzaki (NHMC).
- DOD_009: Karofyllas, 1 m, 13.02.1992, 35.4578N/ 26.9108E, leg. M. Mylonas (NHMC, MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_010: Karpathos, Kofkos, 169 m, 11.07.2006, 35.5686N/ 27.0984E, leg. M. Chatzaki (NHMC, MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_011: Karpathos, Lastos loc. 2, 863 m, 23.05.2014, 35.57415N/ 27.15589E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_012: Karpathos, Agios Loukas, 250 m, 22.05.2014, 35.6008N/ 27.15275E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_013: Karpathos, Agia Kyriaki, 172 m, 24.05.2014, 35.49633N/ 27.23075E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_014: Karpathos, Katodhi, 205 m, 18.05.2014, 35.57519N/ 27.18209E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_015: Karpathos, Achamandria, 292 m, 18.05.2014, 35.68767N/ 27.15036E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_016: Karpathos, Spoa-Mesochori rd., 399 m, 18.05.2014, 21.05.2014, 35.62784N/ 27.12748E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_017: Karpathos, Flaskia Gorge, 67 m, 21.05.2014, 35.5597N/ 27.10981E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_018: Karpathos, Asia Mts., 341 m, 20.05.2014, 35.742N/ 27.14348E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_019: Karpathos, Spoa, 292 m, 20.05.2014, 35.6396N/ 27.14706E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_020: Karpathos, Trachanammos, 17 m, 22.05.2014, 35.45884N/ 27.10244E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).

- DOD_021: Karpathos, Olympos, 429 m, 19.05.2014, 35.72448N/ 27.16972E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_022: Karpathos, Lastos, 724 m, 18.05.2014, 35.57795N/ 27.144E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_023: Karpathos, Avlona, 285 m, 19.05.2014, 35.78039N/ 27.17842E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_024: Karpathos, Panaghia, 302 m, 20.05.2014, 35.69998N/ 27.16666E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_025: Karpathos, Agnondia, 165 m, 18.05.2014, 35.59422N/ 27.16741E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_026: Karpathos, Agios Nikolaos, 205 m, 20.05.2014, 35.63563N/ 27.15231E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_027: Karpathos, Kato Lefkos, 32 m, 21.05.2014, 35.58606N/ 27.08179E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_028: Karpathos, Volada, 658 m, 23.05.2014, 35.55487N/ 27.14741E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_029: Karpathos, Karpathos City, 26 m, 24.05.2014, 35.50667N/ 27.21631E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_030: Karpathos, Spoa-Mesochori loc. 2, 385 m, 22.05.2014, 21.05.2014, 35.63108N/ 27.13624E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_031: Karpathos, Panaghia, 316 m, 20.05.2014, 35.7115N/ 27.17102E, leg. S. Salata (V).
- DOD_032: Karpathos, Finiki, 205 m, 22.05.2014, 35.56133N/ 27.17543E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_033: Kasos, Avlaki, 17 m, 19.02.1992, 35.3478N/ 26.8711E, leg. A. Trichas (NHMC, MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_034: Kasos, Makronisi Island, 12 m, 13.02.1992, 35.4527N/ 25.5486E, leg. Mus. Athens (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_035: Kastellorizo, 70 m, 08.12.1996, 36.1334N/ 29.5677E, leg. Valakos (MNHW-DBET, NHMC).
- DOD_036: Kos, Plaka, 53 m, 06.07.2015, 36.78917N/ 27.0671E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_037: Kos, Paleo Pili loc. 2, 362 m, 07.07.2015, 36.8357N/ 27.19018E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_038: Kos, Zia-Ag. Dimitrios rd. loc. 2, 301 m, 08.07.2015, 36.85047N/ 27.21447E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_039: Kos, Zia, 328 m, 07.07.2015, 36.84555N/ 27.20493E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_040: Kos, Pelli, 270 m, 09.09.2001, 36.8352N/ 27.1668E, leg. M. Chatzaki (NHMC, MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_041: Kos, Paleo Pili loc. 1, 304 m, 07.07.2015, 36.83712N/ 27.18733E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_042: Kos, Aspri Petra, 236 m, 06.07.2015, 36.71857N/ 26.9741E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).

- DOD_043: Kos, Kardamena-Pili rd. loc. 1, 137 m, 07.07.2015, 36.8209N/ 27.15362E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_044: Kos, Kardamena-Pili rd. Loc. 2, 133 m, 07.07.2015, 36.83822N/ 27.15887E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_045: Kos, Zia-Ag. Dimitrios rd. loc. 1, 296 m, 08.07.2015, 36.84755N/ 27.21042E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_046: Kos, Kardamena city, 7 m, 09.07.2015, 36.78363N/ 27.14107E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_047: Kos, Pili, 78 m, 07.07.2015, 36.84185N/ 27.1557E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_048: Kos, Askepion arch. Loc., 79 m, 08.07.2015, 36.87677N/ 27.2593E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_049: Kos, Tigakio salt lake, 1 m, 08.07.2015, 36.88907N/ 27.17485E, leg. S. Salata (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_050: Kounoupoi, 30 m, 11.06.2005, 36.5332N/ 26.467E, leg. M. Chatzaki (NHMC, MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_051: Leros, Lakki-Xerokampos, 80 m, 11.09.2001, 37.1199N/ 26.8656E, leg. M. Chatzaki (NHMC, MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_052: Lytra, 1 m, 17.02.1992, 35.4305N/ 26.8275E, leg. M. Mylonas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_053: Nera, 15 m, 08.06.2005, 36.9138N/ 26.9408E, leg. M. Chatzaki (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_054: Nisyros, rd. Nikia-Avlaki, 290 m, 05.06.2005, 36.5697N/ 27.1872E, leg. M. Chatzaki (NHMC, MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_055: Nisyros, rd. Nikia-Avlaki, 71 m, 05.06.2005, 36.5613N/ 27.1744E, leg. M. Chatzaki (NHMC, MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_056: Nisyros, Moni Evangelistrias, 270 m, 01.06.2005, 36.601N/ 27.151E, leg. M. Chatzaki (MNHW-DBET, NHMC).
- DOD_057: Ofidousa, 100 m, 12.06.2005, 36.551N/ 26.1441E, leg. M. Chatzaki (MNHW-DBET, NHMC).
- DOD_058: Pacheia, 88 m, 06.06.2005, 36.5677N/ 27.0679E, leg. M. Chatzaki (NHMC, MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_059: Rhodes, Faliraki, 4 m, 13.06.2015, 14.06.2015, 15.06.2015, 16.06.2015, 18.06.2015, 21.06.2015, 36.337N/ 28.204E, leg. W. Żyła (USMB).
- DOD_060: Rhodes, n. Faliraki, 6 m, 14.06.2015, 15.06.2015, 18.06.2015, 21.06.2015, 24.06.2015, 27.06.2015, 36.334N/ 28.205E, leg. W. Żyła (USMB).
- DOD_061: Rhodes, Monolithos, 320 m, 28.05.2011, 36.131N/ 27.741E, leg. P. & A. Bezděčkovi (PWC).
- DOD_062: Rhodes, n. Kallithies, 95 m, 19.06.2015, 36.337N/ 28.18E, leg. W. Żyła (USMB).
- DOD_063: Rhodes, 4 km N of Kalathos, 20 m, 16.03.2002, 36.153N/ 28.049E, leg. A. Schulz (PWC).
- DOD_064: Rhodes, 5 km S of Gennadi, 10 m, 21.03.2002, 35.928N/ 27.852E, leg. A. Schulz (PWC).
- DOD_065: Rhodes, 5 Km E of Profitis Ilias, 500 m, 19.03.2002, 36.274N/ 27.978E, leg. A. Schulz (PWC).

- DOD_066: Rhodes, Kolymbia, Hotel Kolymbia Star and vic., 10 m, 03.05.2015, 36.2437N/ 28.15649E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_067: Rhodes, Kolymbia, Tsambika Hill, 157 m, 03.05.2015, 36.23902N/ 28.15942E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_068: Rhodes, Attavyros loc. 1, 669 m, 06.05.2015, 36.19633N/ 27.82456E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_069: Rhodes, Epta Piges, 99 m, 04.05.2015, 36.25459N/ 28.11378E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_070: Rhodes, Petaloudes, 240 m, 08.05.2015, 36.33567N/ 28.06264E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_071: Rhodes, Loytani River, 60 m, 10.07.2006, 36.258N/ 28.1197E, leg. M. Chatzaki (MNHW-DBET, NHMC).
- DOD_072: Rhodes, Attavyros loc. 3, 593 m, 06.05.2015, 36.20018N/ 27.81451E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_073: Rhodes, n. Apollona, 335 m, 06.05.2015, 36.26184N/ 27.97488E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_074: Rhodes, road to Prof. Ilias loc. 2, 522 m, 07.05.2015, 36.27618N/ 27.97216E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_075: Rhodes, Epta Piges, 92 m, 04.07.2008, 36.25N/ 28.01E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_076: Rhodes, Apollona, 372 m, 10.07.2008, 36.25N/ 27.91666E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_077: Rhodes, n. Arhipoli loc. 2, 194 m, 04.05.2015, 05.05.2015, 36.26546N/ 28.06688E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_078: Rhodes, road to Prof. Ilias loc. 4, 589 m, 07.05.2015, 36.27368N/ 27.95618E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_079: Rhodes, Prasonisi-Apollakia, 17 m, 09.07.2006, 35.9676N/ 27.7392E, leg. M. Chatzaki (NHMC, MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_080: Rhodes, Prasonisi, 14 m, 09.07.2006, 35.8842N/ 27.768E, leg. M. Chatzaki (NHMC, MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_081: Rhodes, Kiotari, 3 m, 01.07.2008, 02.07.2008, 05.07.2008, 36.03333N/ 27.95E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_082: Rhodes, Asklipio-Laerma rd., 135 m, 03.07.2008, 36.06666N/ 27.91666E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_083: Rhodes, Agios Nektarios n. Archipoli, 82 m, 04.07.2008, 36.25N/ 28.06666E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_084: Rhodes, Rhodes City, 16 m, 07.07.2008, 36.43333N/ 28.21666E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_085: Rhodes, Mesanagros, 257 m, 08.07.2008, 36N/ 27.81666E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_086: Rhodes, Petaloudes, 192 m, 09.07.2008, 36.33333N/ 28.05E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_087: Rhodes, Attavyros, 1010 m, 08.07.2006, 36.2071N/ 27.8554E, leg. M. Chatzaki (MNHW-DBET).

- DOD_088: Rhodes, road to Prof. Ilias loc. 3, 553 m, 07.05.2015, 36.27233N/ 27.96618E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_089: Rhodes, n. Arhipoli loc. 1, 180 m, 04.05.2015, 36.26164N/ 28.07164E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_090: Rhodes, W of Arhangelos, 115 m, 05.05.2015, 36.21946N/ 28.08732E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_091: Rhodes, Attavyros loc. 2, 598 m, 06.05.2015, 36.19932N/ 27.8187E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_092: Rhodes, road to Prof. Ilias loc. 5, 651 m, 07.05.2015, 36.27546N/ 27.9415E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_093: Rhodes, road to Prof. Ilias loc. 1, 436 m, 07.05.2015, 36.26943N/ 27.98794E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_094: Rhodes, n. Maritsa, 145 m, 08.05.2015, 36.35409N/ 28.09219E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_095: Rhodes, Apolakkia, 34 m, 05.07.2008, 36.05N/ 27.78333E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_096: Rhodes, Agios Nectarios Church, 160 m, 04.05.2015, 36.26574N/ 28.0769E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_097: Rhodes, n. Eleousa, 245 m, 05.05.2015, 36.27223N/ 28.03235E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_098: Rhodes, Kiotari, 12 m, 09.07.2008, 30.06.2008, 36.03333N/ 27.95E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_099: Rhodes, Koprís Hill n. Masari, 59 m, 05.05.2015, 36.17493N/ 28.0439E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_100: Rhodes, Asklipio-Laerma rd., 169 m, 03.07.2008, 36.06666N/ 27.91666E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_101: Rhodes, Dimylia, 91 m, 09.07.2008, 36.33333N/ 28.03333E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_102: Rhodes, Laerma-Apollona rd., 116 m, 06.07.2008, 36.18333N/ 27.95E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_103: Rhodes, Prasonisi-Kattavia rd., 29 m, 01.07.2008, 35.93333N/ 27.76666E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_104: Rhodes, Emponas, 35 m, 10.07.2008, 36.2N/ 27.81666E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_105: Rhodes, Kiotari-Asklipio rd., 59 m, 02.07.2008, 36.05N/ 27.93333E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_106: Rhodes, Gennadi, 8 m, 12.07.2008, 36.03333N/ 27.93333E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_107: Rhodes, Kattavia, 39 m, 05.07.2008, 35.95N/ 27.76666E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_108: Rhodes, Rhodes City, 30 m, 07.07.2008, 36.43333N/ 28.21666E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_109: Rhodes, Prasonisi, 17 m, 09.07.2006, 35.8847N/ 27.7666E, leg. M. Chatzaki (MNHW-DBET).

- DOD_110: Rhodes, 1 km W of Kattavia, 39 m, 05.07.2008, 35.95N/ 27.73333E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_111: Rhodes, Gennadi-Chochlakas rd., 36 m, 12.07.2008, 35.95N/ 27.86666E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_112: Rhodes, Asklipio-Laerma rd., 500 m of Asklipio, 169 m, 03.07.2008, 36.06666N/ 27.91666E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_113: Rhodes, Monolithos-Siana rd., 67 m, 10.07.2008, 36.16666N/ 27.8E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_114: Rhodes, Kattavia-Apolakkia rd., 3 m, 05.07.2008, 36N/ 27.75E, leg. L. Borowiec (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_115: Symi, Panormitis, 120 m, 12.07.2006, 36.5447N/ 27.8465E, leg. M. Chatzaki (NHMC).
- DOD_116: Telendos, Telendos, 14 m, 10.06.2005, 36.9979N/ 26.9201E, leg. M. Chatzaki (NHMC, MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_117: Tilos, Mikro Chorio, 246 m, 24.09.2019, 36.42243N / 27.37098E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_118: Tilos, 1.9 km N of Mikro Chorio, 118 m, 25.09.2019, 36.44002N / 27.37051E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_119: Tilos, Lethra beach, 5 m, 24.09.2019, 36.43757N / 27.38631E, leg. C. Lebas
- DOD_120: Tilos, Megalo Chorio, 110 m, 25.09.2019, 36.4549N / 27.34466E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_121: Tilos, Eristo, 2 m, 25.09.2019, 36.43331N / 27.34749E, leg. C. Lebas.
- DOD_122: Tilos, Ag. Antonios, 1 m, 26.09.2019, 36.45763N / 27.33143E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_123: Tilos, Ag. Pantaleimonas, 247 m, 26.09.2019, 36.44773N / 27.30519E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_124: Tilos, Livadia forest, 26 m, 26.09.2019, 36.40891N / 27.38892E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_125: Tilos, Livadia beach, 3 m, 26.09.2019, 36.4123N / 27.38891E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_126: Tilos, Livadia village, 14 m, 26.09.2019, 36.4543N / 27.38526E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_127: Tilos, Ag. Joannis, 93 m, 27.09.2019, 36.41477N / 27.41E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_128: Tilos, Ag. Nikolaos, 170 m, 27.09.2019, 36.39841N / 27.39452E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_129: Tilos, Livadia Hotel, 9 m, 29.09.2019, 36.41348N / 27.38598E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_130: Tilos, Ag. Pavlos, 278 m, 27.09.2019, 36.40035N / 27.41071E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_131: Tilos, Chapelle Panagis Politissas, 176 m, 27.09.2019, 36.40133N / 27.41071E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_132: Tilos, Plaka, 176 m, 26.09.2019, 36.46278 / 27.30302, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).

- DOD_133: Nisyros, Castro, 99 m, 29.09.2019, 36.60437N / 27.13181E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_134: Nisyros, Loutra, 27 m, 29.09.2019, 36.611277N / 27.15559E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_135: Nisyros, Mandraki, 11 m, 29.09.2019, 36.61016N / 27.13066E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_136: Nisyros, Pali, 11 m, 29.09.2019, 36.61924N / 27.16816E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_137: Nisyros, Nikia, 405 m, 30.09.2019, 36.57505N / 27.17844E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_138: Nisyros, Stefanos Volcano loc. 1, 138 m, 30.09.2019, 36.58177N / 27.17658E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_139: Nisyros, Stefanos Volcano loc. 2, 226 m, 30.09.2019, 36.57561N / 27.15592E, leg. C. Lebas.
- DOD_140: Nisyros, Stefanos Volcano loc. 3, 113 m, 30.09.2019, 36.57926N / 27.16698E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_141: Patmos, Hora (Patmos), 218 m, 03.10.2019, 37.30858N / 26.54755E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_142: Patmos, Grotte de l'Apocalypse, 84 m, 03.10.2019, 37.31525N / 26.54255E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_143: Patmos, Scala, 5 m, 03.10.2019, 37.31525N / 26.54255E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_144: Patmos, Scala harbour, 2 m, 04.10.2019, 37.3236N / 26.54254E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_145: Kalimnos, Chorio, 65 m, 01.10.2019, 36.96331N / 26.95559E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_146: Kalimnos, Platy Gialos, 13 m, 01.10.2019, 36.97423N / 26.92925E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_147: Kalimnos, Pothia harbour, 2 m, 01.10.2019, 36.94994N / 26.98398E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_148: Kalimnos, Pothia centre, 10 m, 1.10.2019, 36.9518N / 26.97885E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_149: Kalimnos, Savvas Monastery, 155 m, 01.10.2019, 36.94381N / 26.98221E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_150: Kalimnos, Kalamies beach, 5 m, 02.10.2019, 37.04426N / 26.93762E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_151: Kalimnos, Palionisos, 2 m, 02.10.2019, 37.04214N / 26.97122E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_152: Kalimnos, Vathis, 3 m, 02.10.2019, 36.97497N / 27.02729E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_153: Kalimnos, Metochi, 48 m, 02.10.2019, 36.98163N / 26.99988E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).
- DOD_154: Rhodes, Rhodes old city, 2 m, 18.09.2019, 36.44152N / 28.22848E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHW-DBET).

- DOD_155: Rhodes, Rhodes new city loc. 1, 83 m, 18.09.2019, 36.44414N / 28.21161E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_156: Rhodes, Faliraki, 4 m, 18.09.2019, 36.33547N / 28.2072E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_157: Rhodes, 1.3 km SE of Asklipio, 125 m, 19.09.2019, 36.06134N / 27.93836E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_158: Rhodes, 2.2 km N of Jennadi, 62 m, 19.09.2019, 36.04386N / 27.91679E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_159: Rhodes, Kephali beach, 3 m, 19.09.2019, 35.97013N / 27.73813E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_160: Rhodes, Lindos loc. 1, 97 m, 19.09.2019, 36.09366N / 28.08074E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_161: Rhodes, Lindos loc. 2, 9 m, 19.09.2019, 36.09368N / 28.08746E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_162: Rhodes, Archangelos, 197 m, 20.09.2019, 36.21046N / 28.11764E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_163: Rhodes, Epta Piges, 104 m, 20.09.2019, 36.25277N / 28.11424E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_164: Rhodes, Charaki, 8 m, 20.09.2019, 36.16679N / 28.09822E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_165: Rhodes, Charaki beach, 5 m, 20.09.2019, 36.1771N / 28.09831E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_166: Rhodes, Ambonas, 346 m, 21.09.2019, 36.25901N / 27.90923E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_167: Rhodes, Chateau Kritinia Castle, 25 m, 21.09.2019, 36.27213N / 27.81725E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_168: Rhodes, Monolothos, 267 m, 21.09.2019, 36.12351N / 27.72691E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_169: Rhodes, Platania, 324 m, 21.09.2019, 36.25463N / 27.98107E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_170: Rhodes, Petaloudes (Butterfly Valley), 212 m, 22.09.2019 36.33719N / 28.05887E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_171: Rhodes, Psinthos, 350 m, 22.09.2019, 36.31679N / 28.08545E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_172: Rhodes, Rhodes new city loc. 2, 5 m, 22.09.2019, 36.45606N / 28.22104E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_173: Rhodes, Rhodes harbour loc. 1, 18 m, 23.09.2019, 36.44702N / 28.22679E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_174: Rhodes, Rhodes harbour loc. 2, 2 m, 23.09.2019, 36.44303N / 28.23822E, leg. C. Lebas (MNHWD-BET).
- DOD_175: Rhodes, Pefkos env., 50 m, 18.09.2011, 36.06N / 28.05E, leg. G. Ruzzante (MNHWD-BET).

LIST OF SPECIES

1. *Acropyga palearctica* MENOZZI, 1936

Published data: Karpathos (MENOZZI 1936: 298, 308); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 26).

Note: It is a rare species recorded from Crete, the Dodecanese, Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly.

2. *Aenictus rhodiensis* MENOZZI, 1936

Published data: Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 266); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 3).

Note: It is a very rare species, in Greece known only from Rhodes of the Dodecanese and Samos of the Aegean Islands.

3. *Aphaenogaster balcanica* (EMERY, 1898)

Locality: 068.

Published data: Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 6).

Note: All records of European species of the *Aphaenogaster testaceopilosa* species-group published before the most recent revision (BOER 2013) require reinvestigation. Recent material from Greece showed that *Aphaenogaster balcanica* is distributed in the Greek mainland, Aegean Islands, Cyclades and Ionian Islands and the only confirmed record from Dodecanese comes from Rhodes, Mt Attavyros.

4. *Aphaenogaster charesi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2016

Localities: 069, 070.

Published data: Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2016: 194).

Note: It is a recently described species, endemic to Rhodes. At the moment known from only two localities.

5. *Aphaenogaster festae* EMERY, 1915

Localities: 036, 037, 038, 069, 071, 072, 073, 074.

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 1, 2, as *Aphaenogaster splendida* ssp. *festae*); Rhodes (Menozzi 1936: 270, as *Aphaenogaster splendida* var. *festae*); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 670, as *Aphaenogaster splendida festae*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 6); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: 138); Kos, Rhodes (SALATA *et al.* 2021: 306).

Note: In Greece it is an eastern species, recorded from Thrace, the Aegean Islands, Cyclades and the Dodecanese.

6. *Aphaenogaster jolantae* BOROWIEC & SALATA, 2014

Localities: 067, 069, 075, 076, 077, 078.

Published data: Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2014b: 48); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2016: 199).

Note: It is a recently described species endemic to Rhodes.

7. *Aphaenogaster karpathica* BOER, 2013

Localities: 010, 011, 012, 013, 014, 015, 016, 017, 018, 019, 020.

Published data: Karpathos (MENOZZI 1936: 263, 270, 307, as *Aphaenogaster testaceopilosa*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194, as *Aphaenogaster balcanica* and *Aphaenogaster ionia*); Karpathos (BOER 2013: 68); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015a: 69).

Note: It is a recently described species endemic to Karpathos.

8. *Aphaenogaster olympica* BOROWIEC & SALATA, 2014

Localities: 016, 017, 021.

Published data: Karpathos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2014b: 52); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015a: 68, 69).

Note: It is a recently described species endemic to Karpathos.

9. *Aphaenogaster simonellii* EMERY, 1894

Published data: Karpathos (BOER 2013: 84).

Note: In Greece it is a common species on Crete. A single record from Karpathos probably based on introduced specimens, because recent investigations on this island have not confirmed its occurrence on Karpathos. All records of *Aphaenogaster simonellii* from the Dodecanese before the BOER's (2013) revision concern other species, probably *Aphaenogaster sporadis*.

10. *Aphaenogaster splendida* (ROGER, 1859)

Locality: 039.

Published data: Kos (SALATA *et al.* 2021: 330).

Note: All historical records from Dodecanese are questionable because this species was confused with more common *Aphaenogaster festae* (SALATA *et al.* 2021).

11. *Aphaenogaster sporadis* SANTSCHI, 1933

Localities: 007, 008 035. 036. 037. 039, 040, 041, 042, 043, 044, 045, 051, 053, 054, 055, 057, 059, 060, 061, 066, 067, 068, 069, 070, 071, 072, 073, 074, 075, 076, 078, 079, 080, 081, 082, 083, 084, 085, 086, 087, 088, 089, 090, 091, 092, 093, 094, 115, 116, 117, 118, 119, 121, 122, 123, 126. 127. 129. 130, 133, 135. 137. 139, 141, 145, 147, 151, 152, 153, 154, 159, 164, 165, 166, 167, 168, 170, 172, 173.

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 1, as *Aphaenogaster simonellii* var. *balcanica*); Nisyros, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1929: 145, as *Aphaenogaster testaceo-pilosa* var. *simonellii*); Rhodes (SANTSCHI 1934: 273, as *Aphaenogaster simonellii* v. *balcanica*); Kalymnos, Kos, Rhodes, Symi (MENOZZI 1936: 263, 270, 307, as *Aphaenogaster testaceo-pilosa* and *Aphaenogaster simonellii* var. *balcanica*); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 670, as *Aphaenogaster testaceopilosa testaceopilosa* and *Aphaenogaster testaceopilosa balcanica*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 8, as *Aphaenogaster simonellii* and *Aphaenogaster testaceopilosa*); Rhodes (BOER 2013: 67); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 467 as *Aphaenogaster simonellii*); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: 138); Nisyros (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015c: 53); Kos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017: 297, 304).

Note: In Greece it is an eastern species, common in the Aegean Islands and the Dodecanese.

12. *Aphaenogaster subcostata* VIEHMAYER, 1922

Locality: 053.

Note: It is a rare species, recorded only from Samos island of the Aegean islands. New to the Dodecanese.

13. *Aphaenogaster subterraneoides* EMERY, 1881

Localities: 002, 003, 005, 007, 035. 050, 053, 056, 057, 116.

Published data: Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 270); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 8).

Note: It is an uncommon species, recorded from the Aegean Islands (Chios), Crete, Cyclades (Christiani and Naxos), the Dodecanese and the Ionian Islands (Corfu and Zakynthos).

14. *Bothriomyrmex communista* SANTSCHI, 1919

Bothriomyrmex jannonei MENOZZI, 1936: 295, new synonymy.

Locality: 037.

Published data: Rhodes (FOREL 1889: 256, as *Bothriomyrmex meridionalis*); Kalymnos (MENOZZI 1936: 263, 295, 308 as *Bothriomyrmex meridionalis* and *Bothriomyrmex jannonei*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 23, as *Bothriomyrmex atlantis* and *Bothriomyrmex jannonei*).

Note: We examined two syntypes of *Bothriomyrmex jannonei* preserved in DSAB and we found no morphological differences between this species and *Bothriomyrmex communista* specimens collected from different regions of Greece. Thus, we propose a synonymization of *Bothriomyrmex jannonei* with *Bothriomyrmex communista*.

It is a common species, recorded from all mainland provinces, the Aegean Islands, the Dodecanese and the Ionian Islands.

15. *Camponotus aegaeus* EMERY, 1915

Localities: 060, 066, 069, 070, 071, 073, 074, 075, 076, 078, 083, 090, 091, 095, 096, 097, 115, 156, 166, 167.

Published data: Rhodes (FOREL 1889: 256, as *Camponotus libanicus*); Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 2, 4, as *Camponotus libanicus* var. *aegaea*); Kos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1929: 146, 304, 308, as *Camponotus libanicus* var. *aegaeus*); Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 264, as *Camponotus libanicus* var. *aegaeus*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 28); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 470); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: 138).

Note: It is an eastern species, recorded from the Aegean Islands, the Dodecanese, Macedonia and Thrace.

16. *Camponotus aethiops* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 040, 042, 051, 068, 080.

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 2, as *Camponotus maculatus aethiops* var. *concava*); Karpathos, Kos (FOREL 1889: 255); Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 2, as *Camponotus aethiops* var. *concava*); Kos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1929: 146); Karpathos, Kos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 264, 300, 308, as *Camponotus aethiops* var. *concava*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 195); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 28, 29, as *Camponotus aethiops* and *Camponotus concavus*); Kos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017: 297).

Note: It is a common species, recorded from all Greek provinces.

17. *Camponotus baldaccii* EMERY, 1908

Localities: 006, 008, 035, 036, 040, 041, 042, 046, 059, 069, 077, 080, 081, 094, 098, 099, 115, 116, 158.

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 2, as *Camponotus maculatus baldaccii*); Jali, Kos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1929: 146, as *Camponotus silvaticus* ssp. *baldaccii*); Jali, Kos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 300, 308 as *Camponotus sylvaticus* ssp. *baldaccii*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD

1993: 195, as *Camponotus cecconii*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 29); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 472); Kos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017: 298, 304).

Note: It is a southern and eastern species, recorded from the Aegean Islands, Crete, the Dodecanese and eastern part of Sterea Ellas.

18. *Camponotus boghossiani* FOREL, 1911

Localities: 039, 042, 044, 069, 070, 072, 074, 076, 077, 078, 081, 086, 088, 091, 092, 093, 094, 096, 097, 100.

Published data: Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 473); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: 138); Kos, Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2018: 7-9).

Note: It is a southern and eastern species, recorded from the Aegean Islands, Crete, Cyclades, the Dodecanese and Peloponnese.

19. *Camponotus candiotes* EMERY, 1894

Localities: 045, 047, 095, 101, 120.

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 2, as *Camponotus lateralis* var. *candiotes*); Kos (MENOZZI 1929: 146, as *Camponotus piceus* var. *candiotes*); Kos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 304, 308); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 677, as *Camponotus lateralis candiotes* and *Camponotus piceus*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 195); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 29); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 473); Rhodes (SEIFERT 2019: 25).

Note: It is a southern species, in Greece recorded only from Crete and the Dodecanese.

20. *Camponotus gestroi* EMERY, 1878

Localities: 003, 004, 008, 011, 012, 015, 021, 022, 023, 024, 044, 053, 054, 067, 068, 099, 118, 127.

Published data: Halki, Symi (FOREL 1889: 256, as *Camponotus gestroi* r. *creticus*); Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 2, as *Camponotus gestroi creticus*); Kos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1929: 146, as *Camponotus gestroi* var. *creticus*); Karpathos, Kos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 302, 308); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 677, as *Camponotus gestroi creticus*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 195); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 30, as *Camponotus creticus* and *Camponotus gestroi*); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015a: 68, 69).

Note: It is an uncommon species recorded from all provinces except Epirus. Populations from Crete, Cyclades and the Dodecanese were classified in the subspecies *Camponotus gestroi creticus* FOREL, 1886 but our materials from Peloponnese showed that there is a clear cline between these populations and the nominotypical subspecies populations (recorded from mainland Greece, the Ionian Islands and the Aegean Islands).

21. *Camponotus ionius* EMERY, 1920

Localities: 010, 012, 014, 015, 016, 017, 019, 021, 024, 025, 026, 027, 028, 029, 096, 129, 149.

Published data: Karpathos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 264, as *Camponotus rubripes cognatus* var. *cognato-pilicornis* and *Camponotus samius* v. *ionia*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 195); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 30); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015a: 68, 69).

Note: It is a common species known from all Greek provinces except Crete.

22. *Camponotus jaliensis* DALLA TORRE, 1893

Localities: 005, 006, 010, 015, 016, 017, 021, 024, 028, 030, 084, 124, 125, 163, 170.

Published data: Jali (FOREL 1889: 255, as *Camponotus rubripes* r. *oertzeni* v. *jaliensis*); Jali (MENOZZI 1936: 264, 300, 308, as *Camponotus aethiops* ssp. *jaliensis*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 195); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 30); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 476); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015: 68, 69).

Note: It is an uncommon species known from islands except Cyclades, noted also from Macedonia and eastern Sterea Ellas.

23. *Camponotus kiesenwetteri* (ROGER, 1859)

Localities: 005, 011, 012, 013, 014, 015, 016, 017, 018, 019, 020, 021, 024, 025, 026, 027, 028, 030, 036, 038, 041, 042, 044, 045, 046, 051, 067, 068, 069, 070, 072, 075, 077, 078, 089, 090, 091, 093, 094, 099, 102, 145, 151, 163, 167.

Published data: Nisyros (FOREL 1889: 255); Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 2, as *Camponotus kiesenwetteri*); Karpathos, Kos, Nisyros, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 304, 308); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 677, as *Camponotus kiesenwetteri*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 195); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 31); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 477); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015a: 68, 69); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: 138); Kos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017: 298, 304).

Note: It is a common species, so far not recorded only from Epirus and Thessaly.

24. *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER, 1792)

Localities: 003, 006, 011, 015, 016, 017, 020, 021, 023, 024, 030, 036, 037, 039, 042, 044, 046, 048, 050, 066, 070, 072, 075, 077, 078, 081, 083, 084, 092, 095, 096, 103, 115, 117, 125, 133, 137, 139, 147, 148, 151, 153, 154, 170.

Published data: Rhodes (FOREL 1889: 256); Karpathos (MENOZZI 1928: 127); Karpathos, Kos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 304, 308 as *Camponotus lateralis* var. *rhodia*); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 674, as *Camponotus fallax pageti*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 31); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 477, 478); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015a: 68, 69, as *Camponotus honaziensis* and *Camponotus lateralis*); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: 138); Kos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017: 298); Rhodes (SEIFERT 2019: 19).

Note: It is one of the commonest Greek ants, recorded from all provinces.

25. *Camponotus oertzeni* FOREL, 1889

Localities: 057, 068, 069, 074, 077, 089, 094, 099, 115.

Published data: Pserimos, Symi (FOREL 1889: 255, as *Camponotus rubripes* r. *oertzeni* and *Camponotus rubripes* r. *oertzeni* var. *kappariensis*); Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 2, 4, as *Camponotus maculatus oertzeni* var. *andria*); Rhodes (SANTSCHI 1934: 280, as *Camponotus aethiops* st. *oertzeni*); Karpathos, Kos, Pserimos, Symi (MENOZZI 1936: 264, 302, 308, as *Camponotus aethiops* var. *andria*, *Camponotus aethiops* ssp. *oertzeni* and *Camponotus aethiops* ssp. *oertzeni* var. *kappariensis*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 28, 30, 31, as *Camponotus andrius*, *Camponotus cappariensis* and *Camponotus oertzeni*); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: 138).

Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces.

26. *Camponotus rebecca* FOREL, 1913

Localities: 070, 075, 086, 095, 101, 104.

Published data: Rhodes (SEIFERT 2019: 22).

Note: It is a rare southern species, recorded only from Crete and the Dodecanese.

27. *Camponotus samius* FOREL, 1889

Localities: 035, 036, 037, 040, 059, 070, 072, 073, 077, 094.

Published data: Karpathos, Kos (FOREL 1889: 255, as *Camponotus rubripes* r. *aethiops*, *Camponotus rubripes* v. *concausus*); Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 2, as *Camponotus maculatus samius*); Rhodes (MENOZZI 1929: 146); Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 300, 308); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 677, as *Camponotus maculatus samius*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 32); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: 138).

Note: It is an uncommon southern and eastern species, recorded from the Aegean Islands, Cyclades, the Dodecanese, Macedonia, Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thrace.

28. *Camponotus sanctus* FOREL, 1904

Localities: 002, 003, 004, 007, 051, 054, 057, 060, 062, 066, 067, 080, 105, 115, 116, 117, 120, 124, 125, 128, 141, 142, 148, 151, 153, 163, 166, 170, 172.

Published data: Halki, Karpathos, Kos, Nisyros, Pserimos, Symi (FOREL 1889: 255, as *Camponotus rubripes* r. *cognatus*, *Camponotus rubripes cognato-pilicornis*, *Camponotus rubripes maculato-dichrous*, *Camponotus rubripes cognato-maculatus-dichrous*); Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 2, as *Camponotus maculatus sanctus* var. *cosensis*); Kos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1929: 146, as *Camponotus compressus* ssp. *sancta* var. *cosensis*); Halki, Kalymnos, Kos, Nisyros, Patmos, Pserimos, Rhodes, Symi (MENOZZI 1936: 264, 300, 308, as *Camponotus compressus* v. *cosensis*, *Camponotus compressus symiensis* and *Camponotus rubripes cognatus* var. *cognato-maculatus*); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 676, as *Camponotus maculatus maculatus*, *Camponotus maculatus silvaticus*, *Camponotus maculatus sanctus*, *Camponotus maculatus variegatus*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 33, as *Camponotus cosensis*, *Camponotus maculatus*, *Camponotus sylvaticus*, *Camponotus symiensis*, *Camponotus sanctus* and *Camponotus variegatus*); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 482).

Note: It is an eastern species, recorded only from the Aegean islands, both northern and southern, including the Dodecanese.

29. *Cardiocondyla bulgarica* FOREL, 1892

Localities: 075, 106.

Published data: Rhodes (SANTSCHI 1934: 277, as *Cardiocondyla elegans* v. *eleonorae*); Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 283 as *Cardiocondyla elegans* var. *eleonora*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 15, 16, as *Cardiocondyla bulgarica* and *Cardiocondyla eleonorae*); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 484).

Note: It is a rare species, recorded from the Aegean Islands, the Dodecanese, Macedonia and Thrace.

30. *Cardiocondyla mauritanica* FOREL, 1890

Localities: 046, 081, 149, 172.

Published data: Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 485); Kos (SALATA *et al.* 2019: 18).

Note: It is a tramp species, in Greece noted in all island provinces. All records are from tourist resorts and urban areas.

31. *Cataglyphis nodus* (BRULLÉ, 1833)

Localities: 006, 008, 036, 041, 042, 046, 048, 049, 051, 054, 055, 059, 060, 066, 070, 075, 079, 080, 081, 089, 090, 094, 099, 102, 117, 118, 121, 123, 130, 133, 134, 139, 140, 151, 153, 159, 167, 169.

Published data: Rhodes (FOREL 1889: 256, as *Myrmecocystus viaticus*); Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 2, as *Cataglyphis bicolor*); Kos, Nisyros, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1929: 146, as *Cataglyphis bicolor*); Jali, Kalymnos, Kos, Nisyros, Rhodes, Telendos (MENOZZI 1936: 264, 305, 308, as *Cataglyphis bicolor* ssp. *nodus*); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 674, as *Cataglyphis bicolor*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 35); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 487); Kos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017: 298, 304).

Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces except Cyclades and a single record from Crete which has been recently questioned (SALATA *et al.* 2020).

32. *Cataglyphis viaticoides* (ANDRÉ, 1881)

Published data: Symi (FOREL 1889: 256, as *Myrmecocystus albicans*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 32, as *Cataglyphis albicans*).

Note: It is a rare species, in Greece recorded only from the Dodecanese, Lesbos and Samos of the Aegean Islands.

33. *Colobopsis truncata* (SPINOLA, 1808)

Localities: 068, 070, 074, 091, 094.

Published data: Rhodes (MENOZZI 1929: 305, 308, as *Camponotus truncatus*); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: 138, as *Camponotus truncatus*).

Note: It is a common species, recorded from all Greek provinces except Cyclades.

34. *Crematogaster erectopilosa* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2015

Localities: 015, 016, 020, 021, 030, 040, 068, 080.

Published data: Kandeliooussa, Karpathos, Kos, Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015a: 65-66).

Note: It is a recently described species known from the Dodecanese and Samos island of the Aegean Islands.

35. *Crematogaster ionia* FOREL, 1911

Localities: 003, 008, 010, 011, 012, 013, 014, 015, 017, 018, 020, 021, 023, 024, 025, 027, 030, 035, 036, 037, 038, 039, 040, 041, 042, 043, 044, 045, 046, 048, 051, 053, 057, 066, 067, 068,

069, 070, 072, 073, 074, 077, 078, 079, 081, 086, 089, 090, 091, 092, 093, 094, 096, 097, 099, 101, 115, 117, 119, 120, 121, 130, 134, 137, 143, 146, 151, 153, 154, 162, 167.

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 1, as *Crematogaster scutellaris schmidti* var. *ionia*); Kalymnos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1928: 127, as *Crematogaster scutellaris* ssp. *schmidti* v. *ionia*); Kos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1929: 146, as *Crematogaster scutellaris* ssp. *schmidti* v. *ionia*); Kalymnos, Karpathos, Kos, Patmos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 263, 283, 307, as *Crematogaster scutellaris* ssp. *schmidti* v. *ionia*); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 672, as *Crematogaster schmidti ionia*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 13); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 488); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015a: 68, 69); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: 138); Kos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017: 298, 304).

Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces.

36. *Crematogaster schmidti* (MAYR, 1853)

Localities: 006, 070, 081, 108, 123.

Published data: Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 489).

Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek Provinces.

37. *Crematogaster sordidula* (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 005, 009, 011, 014, 015, 016, 017, 021, 033, 034.

Published data: Karpathos (MENOZZI 1936: 283, 307, as *Crematogaster sordidula* var. *flachi*); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 672, as *Crematogaster auberti*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 13, as *Crematogaster flachii*); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015a: 68, 69).

Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces.

38. *Cryptopone ochracea* (MAYR, 1855)

Published data: Karpathos (MENOZZI 1936: 269, as *Euponera ochracea*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 3).

Note: It is a rare species, recorded from Crete, the Dodecanese, Macedonia and Peloponnese.

39. *Dolichoderus quadripunctatus* (LINNAEUS, 1771)

Localities: 037, 038, 039, 047.

Note: It is an uncommon species although known from almost all Greek provinces except Cyclades. New to the Dodecanese.

40. *Hypoponera eduardi* (FOREL, 1894)

Published data: Karpathos (MENOZZI 1936: 269, as *Ponera eduardi*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 3).

Note: It is a tramp species, in Greece noted from both natural and anthropogenic habitats. Recorded from the four island provinces, and from Epirus, Macedonia and Peloponnese.

41. *Lasius alienus* (FOERSTER, 1850)

Localities: 070, 078, 151, 153.

Published data: Rhodes (FOREL 1889: 256, as *Lasius alienus*); Kalymnos (MENOZZI 1928: 127, *Lasius niger* ssp. *aliena*); Kalymnos, Karpathos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 264, 305, 308, as *Lasius niger* ssp. *alienus*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 195); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 26).

Note: *Lasius alienus* was recorded from all Greek provinces but due to the recent revision of this genus (SEIFERT 2020) its historical records should be reinvestigated.

42. *Lasius creticus* SEIFERT, 2020

Localities: 018, 036, 041, 066, 069, 071.

Published data: Rhodes (SEIFERT 2020: 57).

Note: It is a recently described species, in Greece known only from Crete and the Dodecanese. Outside Greece recorded from Turkey and Iran.

43. *Lasius illyricus* ZIMMERMANN, 1935

Localities: 070, 078.

Note: It is species common in northern Greece and the Ionian Islands, rare in Crete and the Aegean islands. Recorded from most Greek provinces except Cyclades and, until now, the Dodecanese. New to the Dodecanese.

44. *Lasius lasioides* (EMERY, 1869)

Localities: 039, 045, 046, 070, 075, 081, 103, 142.

Published data: Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 502); Rhodes (SEIFERT 2020: supplementary information).

Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces.

45. *Lasius neglectus* VAN LOON *et al.*, 1990

Localities: 071.

Published data: Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 27); Rhodes (SEIFERT 2020: supplementary information).

Note: It is an uncommon species, recorded from the Aegean Islands, Cyclades, the Dodecanese, Peloponnese and Thrace.

46. *Lasius precursor* SEIFERT, 2020

Published data: Kos (SEIFERT 2020: 51).

Note: It is a recently described species, in Greece known only from the Dodecanese. Outside Greece recorded from Turkey.

47. *Lasius turcicus* SANTSCHI, 1921

Localities: 018, 037, 045, 047, 066, 069, 090, 094, 107, 108, 123, 124, 137, 154, 156.

Published data: Karpathos (MENOZZI 1928: 127, *Lasius niger* ssp. *turcica*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 27); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 506); Kos, Rhodes (SEIFERT 2020: 54 and supplementary information).

Note: It is an uncommon species, recorded from all Greek provinces except Thessaly.

48. *Lepisiota* cf. *caucasica* _KAROFYLLAS

Locality: 009.

Note: It is a species of unclear status, belonging to the speciose *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* species-group. Known only from the Karyofyllas island.

49. *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR, 1855)

Locality: 022.

Published data: Karpathos (MENOZZI 1928: 127; Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 195, as *Acantholepis frauenfeldi*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 24).

Note: It is a common species recorded from all Greek provinces except Cyclades. In the Dodecanese typical morphospecies is known only from Karpathos, morphospecies from Kalymnos, Kos, Leros, Rhodes and Telendos appears to be a distinct population now of unclear status.

50. *Lepisiota* cf. *frauenfeldi* _AEGEAN

Localities: 046, 075, 085, 095, 103, 105, 108, 110, 151, 153

Note: It is another species of unclear status belonging to the speciose *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* species-group. Recorded only from the Aegean Islands and the Dodecanese.

51. *Lepisiota melas* (EMERY, 1915)

Localities: 006, 036, 038, 040, 041, 042, 054, 055, 056, 058, 060, 067, 068, 070, 072, 073, 074, 077, 080, 084, 091, 094, 096, 097, 101, 109, 117, 118, 120, 122, 123, 127, 129, 133, 134, 135, 137, 139, 141, 142, 143, 144, 145, 149, 152, 154, 159, 162, 163, 166, 172.

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 2, 3, as *Acantholepis frauenfeldi* var. *melas*); Rhodes (SANTSCHI 1934: 280, as *Acantholepis frauenfeldi* var. *melas*); Halki, Kalymnos, Karpathos, Kasos, Kos, Nisyros, Rhodes, Telendos, Tilos (MENOZZI 1936: 264, 298, 308, as *Acantholepis frauenfeldi* v. *melas*); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 673, as *Acantholepis frauenfeldi melas*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 24); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 507, as *Lepisiota frauenfeldi*); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: 138); Kos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017: 298, 304).

Note: It was recorded from most of the Greek provinces except Epirus and Thrace.

52. *Lepisiota* cf. *melas* _ KARPATHOS

Localities: 013, 014, 022, 026, 029.

Published data: Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015: 69, as *Lepisiota melas*);

Note: Populations recorded from Karpathos as *Lepisiota melas* appear to be a distinct species. Its status will be clarified in a future revision of the entire *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* species-group.

53. *Lepisiota nigra* (DALLA TORRE, 1893)

Localities: 012, 014, 015, 016, 021, 024, 027, 094.

Published data: Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 195, as *Acantholepis splendens*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 24, 25, as *Lepisiota nigra* and *Lepisiota splendens*); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015: 68, 69).

Note: It is a western species, verified records are from Crete, the Dodecanese, Ionian Islands, Peloponnese and Sterea Ellas.

54. *Lepisiota syriaca* (ANDRÉ, 1881)

Localities: 051, 116.

Published data: Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 509, as *Lepisiota* cf. *syriaca*); Leros, Rhodes, Telendos (SALATA *et al.* 2019: 16).

Note: This is an invasive species recorded from Crete, Attica in Sterea Ellas and from the Dodecanese, observed only in tourist resorts and urban areas.

55. *Leptanilla* sp. 1

Published data: Rhodes (WARD & SUMNICH 2012: 7).

Note: One of the three species of Greek *Leptanilla* known only from males collected at light.

56. *Leptanilla* sp. 2

Published data: Rhodes (WARD & SUMNICH 2012: 8).

Note: One of the three species of Greek *Leptanilla* known only from males collected at light.

57. *Leptanilla* sp. 3

Published data: Rhodes (WARD & SUMNICH 2012: 8).

Note: One of the three species of Greek *Leptanilla* known only from males collected at light.

58. *Messor carpathous* MENOZZI, 1936

Localities: 023, 026.

Published data: Karpathos (MENOZZI, 1936: 277, as *Messor oertzeni* var. *carpathous*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 9, as *Messor alexandrii* and *Messor carpathous*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194, as *Messor oertzeni*); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2019b: 54).

Note: It is a species endemic to Karpathos.

59. *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987

Localities: 092.

Published data: Dodecanese (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2019b: 66).

Note: Known from almost all Greek provinces except the Ionian Islands, common in mainland, rare on islands.

60. *Messor ibericus* SANTSCHI, 1927

Localities: 003, 008, 058, 085, 098, 110, 157.

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 1, as *Messor barbarus clivorum*); Karpathos (MENOZZI 1928: 126, as *Messor structor* var. *aegaea*); Karpathos, Kasos, Patmos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 276, 307, as *Messor structor* var. *aegaea*); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 671, as *Messor clivorum*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 9, as *Messor aegaeus*); Agia Kyriaki, Kalymnos, Pacheia, Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2019b: 61, 62).

Note: It is a common species but still unrecorded from the Aegean Islands, Cyclades and Sterea Ellas.

61. *Messor mcarthuri* STEINER *et al.*, 2018

Localities: 012, 014, 021, 022, 023, 024, 025, 029, 037, 039, 042, 046, 047, 059, 060, 117, 118, 119, 123, 126, 127, 129, 131, 132, 134, 135, 136, 138, 140, 142, 143, 145, 147, 148, 152, 161, 162, 164, 165, 166.

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 1, as *Messor barbarus structor* var. *mutica*); Rhodes (SANTSCHI 1934: 275, as *Messor structor* st. *muticus*); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 671, as *Messor structor mutica*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194, as *Messor orientalis*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 11, as *Messor muticus* and *Messor orientalis*); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 514, as *Messor muticus*); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015a: 68, as *Messor orientalis*); Kos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017: 298, as *Messor orientalis*); Karpathos, Kos, Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2019b: 63, 64).

Note: It is a recently described species previously confused with other species of the *Messor structor* species group (STEINER *et al.* 2018). Confirmed records are from the Aegean Islands, Crete, the Dodecanese, Macedonia, Peloponnese, Thessaly and Thrace.

62. *Messor oertzeni* FOREL, 1910

Published data: Kos (MENOZZI 1936: 276); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 9).

Note: It is an eastern species recorded only from the Aegean Islands, the Dodecanese, northern Macedonia and Thrace.

63. *Messor* cf. *semirufus*

Localities: 046, 117, 125, 133, 136, 139, 140, 175.

Note: This is probably an undescribed species, a member of the *Messor semirufus* species-

group. In Greece occur three morphospecies from this group. Their status is unclear, as this group is speciose in the eastern part of the Mediterranean Basin and needs comprehensive revision. Probably all three Greek morphospecies belong to one or more undescribed species.

64. *Messor varrialei* EMERY, 1921

Localities: 067, 069, 081.

Published data: Rhodes (SANTSCHI 1934: 275, as *Messor structor* v. *aegeus*); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2019b: 65).

Note: It is a species of unclear status, perhaps only a form of *Messor mcarthuri*. Hitherto known only from Rhodes, one locality on Lesbos of the Aegean Islands and western Turkey.

65. *Messor wasmanni* KRAUSSE, 1910

Localities: 007, 008, 013, 014, 016, 020, 021, 022, 023, 024, 028, 029, 042, 046, 054, 066, 068, 081, 094, 098, 111, 117, 127, 128, 130, 141, 155, 159, 160, 161, 164, 167, 169, 171, 172, 173.

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 1, as *Messor barbarus semirufus* var. *concolor*); Rhodes (SANTSCHI 1934: 275, as *Messor semirufus* v. *meridionalis* and *Messor semirufus* v. *intermedius*); Kalymnos, Karpathos, Kasos, Kos, Rhodes, Tilos (MENOZZI 1936: 263, 276, 307 as *Messor semirufus* var. *meridionalis*); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 671, as *Messor semirufus concolor*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 10, 12, as *Messor concolor*, *Messor meridionalis* and *Messor wasmanni*); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 516); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015a: 68, 69); Kos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017: 298).

Note: One of the commonest Greek ants, recorded from all provinces.

66. *Monomorium bicolor* EMERY, 1877

Localities: 002, 003, 009, 020, 024, 025, 029, 050, 057.

Published data: Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194, as *Monomorium phoenicium*); Karpathos (SALATA *et al.* 2019: 19).

Note: It is an invasive species, recorded only from the Aegean Islands, Crete, Cyclades and the Dodecanese, observed mostly in tourist resorts and urban areas.

67. *Monomorium pharaonis* (LINNAEUS, 1758)

Published data: Rhodes (MENOZZI 1928: 127). Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 283, 307); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 15).

Note: It is an indoor species recorded from the Aegean Islands, Crete, Cyclades, the Dodecanese and Macedonia.

68. *Monomorium subopacum* (SMITH, 1858)

Localities: 027, 046, 081, 116, 119, 120, 126, 129, 156.

Published data: Karpathos (MENOZZI 1928: 127, as *Monomorium bicolor* ssp. *nitidiventris*); Alinia, Kalymnos, Karpathos, Kasos, Kos, Rhodes, Telendos (MENOZZI 1936: 283, 307, as *Monomorium bicolor* ssp. *nitidiventris*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194, as *Monomorium nitidiventre*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 14, as *Monomorium nitidiventre*); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 519); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015: 69); Karpathos, Rhodes (SALATA *et al.* 2019: 20).

Note: It is an invasive species, recorded only from the Aegean Islands, Crete, Cyclades and the Dodecanese, observed mostly in tourist resorts and urban areas.

69. *Myrmecina graminicola* (LATREILLE, 1802)

Published data: Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 285, 307); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 12).

Note: It is an uncommon species, but recorded from almost all the Greek provinces except the Aegean Islands.

70. *Nylanderia jaegerskioeldi* (MAYR, 1904)

Localities: 011, 029, 046, 047, 066, 098, 125, 136, 143, 144, 146, 147, 149, 172, 173.

Published data: Rhodes (FOREL 1889: 256, as *Prenolepis vividula*); Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 264, 308, as *Paratrechina jaegerskioeldi*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 195); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 25); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 525); Karpathos, Kos, Rhodes (SALATA *et al.* 2019: 15).

Note: It is an invasive species, recorded from the Aegean islands (Samos), Crete, the Dodecanese, the Ionian Islands (Cephalonia, Zakynthos), Peloponnese and Sterea Ellas, noted only from tourist resorts and urban areas.

71. *Oxyopomyrmex krueperi* FOREL, 1911

Published data: Karpathos (MENOZZI 1936: 278, as *Oxyopomyrmex lagoi*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 12); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015c: 15).

Note: It is a rare species, recorded only from Crete, the Dodecanese and Macedonia.

72. *Oxyopomyrmex polybotesi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2015

Localities: 063, 064.

Published data: Nisyros (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015c: 50).

Note: It is a recently described species, in Greece known only from Nisyros of the Dodecanese, Samos of the Aegean islands. Outside Greece recorded also from İzmir and Muğla provinces of western Turkey.

73. *Paratrechina longicornis* (LATREILLE, 1802)

Localities: 146, 149, 150, 172.

Note: It is an invasive species, recorded only generally from Greece (KUGLER 1988). Our data are the first exact records from Greece. New for the Dodecanese.

74. *Pheidole indica* MAYR, 1879

Localities: 029, 046, 084, 122, 143, 149, 154, 158, 172, 173.

Published data: Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194, as *Pheidole teneriffana*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 12, as *Pheidole teneriffana*); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 527, as *Pheidole teneriffana*); Karpathos, Kos, Rhodes (SALATA *et al.* 2019: 16).

Note: It is an invasive species, recorded from all island provinces and from Peloponnese. Noted mostly from urban areas and tourist resorts.

75. *Pheidole pallidula* complex

Localities: 008, 009, 010, 012, 013, 015, 016, 017, 019, 020, 021, 022, 023, 024, 025, 026, 029, 030, 036, 037, 038, 039, 040, 041, 042, 043, 045, 046, 047, 048, 051, 054, 055, 056, 059,

066, 067, 068, 069, 070, 071, 073, 077, 078, 080, 081, 083, 090, 091, 094, 099, 105, 112, 115, 116, 118, 120, 121, 122, 125, 126, 127, 129, 130, 131, 132, 135, 137, 139, 141, 147, 148, 150, 151, 153, 154, 156, 159, 165, 170.

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 1, as *Pheidole pallidula* var. *orientalis*); Karpathos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1928: 126 as *Pheidole pallidula* var. *orientalis*); Rhodes (SANTSCHI 1934: 276, as *Pheidole pallidula* st. *arenarium* v. *orientalis*); Kalymnos, Karpathos, Kasos, Kos, Patmos, Rhodes, Telendos, Tilos (MENOZZI 1936: 263, 279, 307, as *Pheidole pallidula* v. *orientalis*); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 672, as *Pheidole pallidula orientalis*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194, as *Pheidole pallidula*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 12, as *Pheidole pallidula*); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 527, as *Pheidole pallidula*); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015a: 68, 69, as *Pheidole pallidula*); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: 138, as *Pheidole koshewnikovi*); Kos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017: 298, 304, as *Pheidole pallidula*); Kos, Rhodes (SEIFERT 2016: 3, as *Pheidole koshewnikovi*).

Note: It is one of the commonest Greek ants. Mediterranean populations of the taxon named *Pheidole pallidula* (NYLANDER, 1849) have recently been divided into four species, three of them recorded in Greece (SEIFERT 2016), but this revision is still under discussion owing to the great local variability of this very common Mediterranean ant. SEIFERT (2016) noted from the Dodecanese only *Pheidole koshewnikovi* RUSZKY, 1905.

76. *Plagiolepis pallescens* FOREL, 1889

Localities: 006, 007, 009, 011, 014, 015, 016, 022, 023, 024, 025, 036, 039, 048, 054, 055, 066, 067, 068, 069, 070, 072, 074, 077, 078, 081, 083, 088, 089, 090, 093, 094, 097, 099, 113, 118, 119, 122, 125, 129, 130, 131, 133, 141, 142, 143, 144, 150, 152, 156, 165, 170, 172, 173.

Published data: Karpathos, Kasos, Rhodes (FOREL 1889: 256, as *Plagiolepis pygmaea*); Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 1, as *Plagiolepis pygmaea*); Kalymnos, Karpathos, Kasos, Kos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 264, 297, 308); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 673, as *Plagiolepis pygmaea*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 195); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 25, as *Plagiolepis pygmaea*); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 529, as *Plagiolepis taurica*); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015a: 69, as *Plagiolepis taurica*); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: 138, as *Plagiolepis taurica*); Karpathos, Kalymnos, Karofyllas, Kos, Nisyfos, Rhodes (SALATA *et al.* 2018a: 812).

Note: It is a common species, recorded from all Greek provinces except Epirus.

77. *Plagiolepis perperamus* SALATA, BOROWIEC & RADCHENKO, 2018

Localities: 016, 020, 021, 024, 026, 027, 030, 043, 045, 046.

Published data: Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 25, as *Plagiolepis pallescens*); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015: 68, 69, as *Plagiolepis pallescens* sensu Radchenko); Karpathos, Kos (SALATA *et al.* 2018: 817).

Note: It is an uncommon species but known from all Greek provinces.

78. *Proceratium melinum* (ROGER, 1860)

Published data: Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 4); Karpathos, Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2018: 22).

Note: It is a rare species, recorded from the Dodecanese, the Ionian Islands, Peloponnese and Sterea Ellas.

79. *Solenopsis crivellarii* MENOZZI, 1936

Published data: Karpathos (MENOZZI 1936: 284, 307); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 15).

Note: It is a species of unclear status, hitherto known only from the Dodecanese and Crete.

80. *Stigmatomma denticulatum* ROGER, 1859

Published data: Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 268, as *Stigmatomma denticulatum* var. *gracilicornis*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 3, as *Amblyopone denticulata*).

Note: It is a rare species but known from almost all island provinces except Cyclades, and from Epirus, Peloponnese and Thrace.

81. *Strongylognathus huberi dalmaticus* URBANI, 1969

Published data: Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 195); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 20).

Note: It is a rare social parasite of some *Tetramorium* species, recorded only from the Dodecanese, Crete, the Ionian Islands and Peloponnese. Record from Karpathos needs confirmation as it may be based on misidentification with the very similar *Strongylognathus silvestrii*.

82. *Strongylognathus silvestrii* MENOZZI, 1936

Published data: Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 292, 308).

Note: It is a rare social parasite of some *Tetramorium* species, recorded only from Crete, the Dodecanese and Peloponnese.

83. *Tapinoma* cf. *erraticum*_BALC

Locality: 068.

Note: According to B. Seifert's note in WAGNER *et al.* (2018), populations of *Tapinoma erraticum* in south-eastern Europe consist of a complex of two similar species easily separated by the morphology of male genitalia. They suggested that the true *T. erraticum* is common only in northern parts of the Balkan Peninsula. In the Greek material, we found only morphospecies identified by WAGNER *et al.* (2018) as *Tapinoma* cf. *erraticum*_BALC. Examined specimens come from Crete, the Cyclades, the Dodecanese, the East Aegean Is., Epirus, the Ionian Is., Macedonia, Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace. First certain record for the Dodecanese.

84. *Tapinoma festae* EMERY, 1925

Localities: 046, 048, 049, 066, 083, 106, 154, 156, 172, 174.

Published data: Karpathos, Kos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 263, 295, 308, as *Tapinoma simrothi* ssp. *festae*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 23).

Note: It is noted from all island provinces, at the moment with no records from mainland Greece.

85. *Tapinoma simrothi* KRAUSSE, 1911

Localities: 013, 020, 021, 023, 024, 025, 032, 057, 114, 120, 121, 129, 131, 132, 174.

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 1, as *Tapinoma erraticum nigerrimum*); Karpathos, Kos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 295, 308, as *Tapinoma simrothi* var. *phoenicia*); EMERY 1925b; Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 673, as *Tapinoma nigerrimum*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 195); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 23, 24, as *Tapinoma erraticum*, *Tapinoma phoeniceum*

and *Tapinoma simrothi*); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 538, as *Tapinoma nigerrimum*); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015: 68, 69).

Note: It is an uncommon species although known from all Greek provinces except Epirus.

86. *Temnothorax aeolius* (FOREL, 1911)

Published data: Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 291, 308, as *Leptothorax bulgaricus* ssp. *aeolius*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 17).

Note: It is a rare species recorded from the Aegean Island, Cyclades, the Dodecanese, Macedonia and Thrace.

87. *Temnothorax antigoni* (FOREL, 1911)

Localities: 038, 044, 070, 072, 074, 091, 093, 165.

Published data: Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: supplementary data).

Note: It is an eastern species, in Greece common in the Aegean Islands and the eastern Dodecanese islands.

88. *Temnothorax bulgaricus* (FOREL, 1892)

Localities: 037, 038, 039, 078, 157.

Published data: Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 291, 308, as *Leptothorax bulgaricus* ssp. *graecus*).

Note: It is a common species although not recorded from Crete and Cyclades.

89. *Temnothorax dessyi* (MENOZZI, 1936)

Localities: 070, 072, 077, 091.

Published data: Karpathos (MENOZZI 1936: 289, 308, as *Leptothorax dessyi*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 18); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: 138); Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2018: 26).

Note: It is a rare species, known only from Karpathos and Rhodes of the Dodecanese and two localities in northern Peloponnese.

90. *Temnothorax* cf. *exilis*

Localities: 006, 009, 010, 014, 011, 015, 016, 017, 019, 021, 023, 024, 030, 058, 067, 070, 078, 091, 124, 125.

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 1, 2, as *Temnothorax exilis* var. *darius*); Karpathos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 287, 289, 307, as *Leptothorax exilis* var. *darii* and *Leptothorax exilis* ssp. *cretica*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194, as *Leptothorax exilis*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 17, 18, as *Temnothorax creticus*, *Temnothorax darii* and *Temnothorax exilis*); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015: 68, 69, as *Temnothorax exilis*).

Note: The *Temnothorax exilis* complex from Greece needs extensive revision. There are at least 7 morphospecies of unclear taxonomic status collected in this country. Specimens from Dodecanese belong to the three morphospecies with mostly dark body coloration. Until the revision of the whole group their status remains unclear. Various morphospecies of the whole *Temnothorax exilis* species-group were recorded from all Greek provinces.

91. *Temnothorax* cf. *ionia*

= *Temnothorax bulgaricus* ssp. *smyrnensis* var. *ionia* FOREL, 1911: 336.

Localities: 036, 039, 042, 065, 070, 077, 099.

Note: It is a morphospecies conspecific with taxon described as *Temnothorax bulgaricus* ssp. *smyrnensis* var. *ionia* FOREL. but the name is unavailable to nomenclature and its formal description will be published in the prepared revision of the *Temnothorax graecus* species-group. In our material we have samples of this taxon from the Aegean Islands and the Dodecanese.

92. *Temnothorax kemali* (SANTSCHI, 1934)

Localities: 038, 070, 077, 091, 097, 139, 152.

Published data: Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2018: 29).

Note: It is an eastern species, we examined samples from the Aegean Islands and the Dodecanese.

93. *Temnothorax* cf. *luteus*

Localities: 057, 069, 070, 077, 078, 089, 099, 115.

Note: It is an undescribed species at first glance similar to the western Mediterranean members of the *Temnothorax luteus* species-group. We examined samples of this morphospecies only from the Dodecanese.

94. *Temnothorax recedens* (NYLANDER, 1856)

Localities: 011, 015, 021, 024.

Published data: Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194, as *Leptothorax recedens*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 19); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015: 68, 69) Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: supplementary data).

Note: It is a widely distributed species, recorded from all Greek provinces but in the Dodecanese rare.

95. *Temnothorax rogeri* EMERY, 1869

Published data: Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194, as *Leptothorax rogeri*).

Note: It is a western species, recorded from Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Peloponnese and western Sterea Ellas. Its occurrence in the Dodecanese should be confirmed, perhaps there has been a misidentification with *Temnothorax solerii* (MENOZZI, 1936).

96. *Temnothorax semiruber* (ANDRÉ, 1881)

Published data: Karpathos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 285, 307, as *Leptothorax rottenbergi* ssp. *semiruber* var. *galatica*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194, as *Leptothorax semiruber*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 18, 19, as *Temnothorax galatica* and *Temnothorax semiruber*); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015: 69).

Note: It is an uncommon species although recorded from all Greek provinces except Ionian Islands.

97. *Temnothorax smyrnensis* (FOREL, 1911)

Localities: 038, 039, 044.

Published data: Kos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2018: 32).

Note: It is an eastern species, in Greece recorded only from the Aegean Island and the Dodecanese.

98. *Temnothorax solerii* (MENOZZI, 1936)

Localities: 010, 011, 013, 015, 017, 018, 019, 021, 024, 025, 028.

Published data: Karpathos (MENOZZI 1936: 291, 308, as *Leptothorax solerii*); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015: 68, 69); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015b: supplementary data).

Note: It is a species endemic to Karpathos.

99. *Tetramorium diomedeam* EMERY, 1908

Localities: 008, 054, 055, 067, 069, 099, 114, 149.

Published data: Published data: Karpathos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 292, 308, as *Tetramorium ferox* var. *laevior*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 21, as *Tetramorium laevior*); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 549).

Note: It is an uncommon species although noted from most Greek provinces except Cyclades, Sterea Ellas and Thrace.

100. *Tetramorium ferox* RUZSKY, 1903

Locality: 159.

Published data: LEGAKIS 2011: 21; SALATA & BOROWIEC 2018: 50.

Note: It is recorded from all island provinces, Macedonia and Thrace.

101. *Tetramorium* cf. *flavidulum*

Locality: 054.

Note: It is a distinct species belonging to the *Tetramorium flavidulum* species-group. Perhaps an undescribed species but the group is speciose in Anatolia and before the revision of Anatolian members of this group status of the population from Nisyros remains unclear.

102. *Tetramorium hippocratis* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987

Localities: 041, 042, 133, 148.

Published data: KOS (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017: 300).

Note: It is a southern and eastern species, recorded from the Aegean Islands, Crete, the Dodecanese and Thrace.

103. *Tetramorium immigrans* SANTSCHI, 1927

Localities: 066, 143, 144.

Published data: Rhodes (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2019a: 5).

Note: It is a tramp species of subcosmopolitan distribution. In Greece, it was noted from most provinces except Cyclades and Epirus.

104. *Tetramorium indocile* SANTSCHI, 1927

Localities: 026.

Published data: Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2019a: 6).

Note: It is a species widely distributed in the western Palaearctic but usually confused with *Tetramorium caespitum* (WAGNER *et al.* 2017). In Greece, noted only from Crete, the Dodecanese and Macedonia.

105. *Tetramorium kephalosi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2017

Localities: 003, 005, 007, 009, 014, 023, 051, 054, 055, 057, 058, 071, 081, 110, 114, 116, 152, 159.

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 1, as *Tetramorium caespitum* var. *semilaeve*); Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 292, 308, as *Tetramorium semilaeve* var. *galatica*); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 673, as *Tetramorium caespitum semilaeve*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 22, as *Tetramorium semilaeve*); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 549, as *Tetramorium semilaeve*); Kos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017: 291).

Note: It is a recently described species confused with *Tetramorium semilaeve* ANDRÉ, 1883. In Greece appears to be a very common species, known from all Greek provinces.

106. *Tetramorium meridionale* EMERY, 1870

Published data: Karpathos (LEGAKIS 2011: 21).

Note: LEGAKIS (2011) noted this species from Karpathos citing COLLINGWOOD (1933) as the source of this information, but this species is not mentioned in Collingwood's work. We do not exclude the presence of this species in the Dodecanese as we have examined specimens from *Tetramorium meridionale* species-group collected in the Aegean part of Turkey. Its occurrence in the Dodecanese needs confirmation.

107. *Tetramorium* cf. *punctatum*

Localities: 008, 009, 011, 014, 016, 017, 018, 022, 024, 026, 046, 054, 055, 127, 129, 138.

Published data: Karpathos, Kos, Patmos, Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 292, 308, as *Tetramorium semilaeve* var. *siciliensis*); Karpathos (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015: 69).

Note: There are at least two Greek morphospecies with characters of workers similar to those occurring in *Tetramorium punctatum* SANTSCHI, 1927, known from Italy (SANETRA *et al.* 1999). Nevertheless, gyne characters of Greek taxa suggest that both species are not conspecific with true *T. punctatum*. A proper identification of species of this group requires complete nest samples, with workers, gynes and males. Since we did not collect males in Greek samples, their taxonomic status needs further studies.

108. *Tetramorium rhodium* EMERY, 1924

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 1, 3, as *Tetramorium caespitum caespitum* var. *rhodia*); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 673, as *Tetramorium caespitum rhodia*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 22).

Note: It is an eastern species, in Greece recorded only from the Aegean Islands and the Dodecanese.

109. *Tetramorium sulcinode* SANTSCHI, 1927

Localities: 054.

Published data: Nisyros (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2019a: 2).

Note: It is a species distributed mostly in Central Asia with occurrence decreasing towards the west. Locality on the island of Nisyros is the westernmost for this species.

110. *Trichomyrmex perplexus* RADCHENKO, 1997

Localities: 054, 055, 056, 066, 067, 105, 116, 121, 138, 139, 147, 152, 161, 162.

Published data: Rhodes (EMERY 1915: 1, as *Monomorium dentigerum*); Karpathos, Kasos,

Rhodes (MENOZZI 1936: 284, 307, as *Monomorium dentiger*); Rhodes (HAMANN & KLEMM 1976: 672, as *Halcomyrmex dentiger*); Karpathos (COLLINGWOOD 1993: 194, as *Monomorium dentigerum*); Dodecanese (LEGAKIS 2011: 14, as *Monomorium dentigerum*); Rhodes (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012: 518, as *Monomorium dentigerum*).

Note: It is an uncommon species known from most Greek provinces except Epirus and Thrace.

DISCUSSION

The Dodecanese, although consisting of rather small or moderate islands, appears to be rich in ant species. So far, there are 110 species recorded from this archipelago, and this number is higher than ant diversity noted from Crete, the largest Greek Island with 100 reported species (SALATA *et al.* 2020), and from Euboea, the second largest island with 71 reported species (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018e). While comparing other Greek archipelagos, only the Aegean Islands have a higher number of species – 118 (our unpublished data), while the Ionian Islands host 92 species (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2021), and Cyclades only 56 (our unpublished data). With six endemic species, the Dodecanese clearly gives way to Crete from which we know 18 endemics. Generally, ants of the Dodecanese belong to the Aegean complex of species, as many as 38 species are common with ant fauna of the Aegean islands. Chorologically in the Dodecanese predominate species of Mediterranean chorotypes – 76 (69%).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Thanks to Roland Dobosz (USMB, Poland), Giovanni Bazzocchi (DSAB, Italy), Apostolos Trichas (NHMC, Greece), and Petr Werner (PWC) for sharing the ant material preserved in these collections, and to Claude Lebas (Canohès, France) for donating to the collection of the Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław (Poland) numerous materials of ants collected in the Dodecanese. Lech Borowiec thanks Jolanta Świętojańska (University of Wrocław) for her assistance during field trips.

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Figs. 1–6. Endemic species of ants from the Dodecanese: 1 – *Aphaenogaster charesi* SALATA & BOROWIEC (scale bar = 2 mm), 2 – *Aphaenogaster jolantae* BOROWIEC & SALATA (scale bar = 1 mm), 3 – *Aphaenogaster karpathica* BOER (scale bar = 1 mm), 4 – *Aphaenogaster olympica* BOROWIEC & SALATA (scale bar = 1 mm), 5 – *Temnothorax solerii* (Menozi) (scale bar = 0.5 mm), 6 – *Messor carpathous* MENOZZI (scale bar = 1 mm).

Accepted: 19 September 2021; published: 15 October 2021

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